

MODERN STRATEGIES FOR THE TREATMENT OF COPD CONSIDERING SYSTEMIC MANIFESTATIONS AND KIDNEY INVOLVEMENT

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Abstract. *Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a multifactorial condition characterized not only by damage to the respiratory system but also by pronounced systemic manifestations, including endothelial dysfunction, oxidative stress, and comorbidities. Cardiovascular and renal complications, driven by shared pathogenetic mechanisms such as chronic inflammation, hypoxia, and microcirculatory disorders, have the greatest clinical significance. This review presents current insights into the pathogenesis of COPD in the context of comorbidity, with an emphasis on the role of systemic inflammation, endothelial dysfunction, and activation of free radical processes. Both pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatment approaches are discussed, including bronchodilators, inhaled corticosteroids, phosphodiesterase-4 inhibitors, antioxidants, antihypoxants, as well as risk factor modification measures and pulmonary rehabilitation. Special attention is given to the interplay between COPD and chronic kidney disease, as well as the prospects for combined therapeutic strategies aimed at correcting systemic disorders and improving patient outcomes. The presented data highlight the need for a comprehensive approach to COPD management, taking into account the individual course of the disease and associated comorbidities.*

Keywords: *chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, comorbidity, endothelial dysfunction, oxidative stress, chronic kidney disease, antioxidants, antihypoxants, comprehensive therapy.*

Introduction

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is one of the most common respiratory diseases and a leading cause of mortality worldwide. According to GOLD and large-scale epidemiological studies, COPD ranks third among the causes of death, surpassed only by cardiovascular and oncological diseases [1]. In addition to progressive airflow limitation, the disease is characterized by systemic inflammatory responses involving the cardiovascular, renal, and other organ systems [2].

Pharmacological therapy for COPD includes the use of bronchodilators, which dilate the airways and reduce the severity of obstruction, as well as combinations of inhaled glucocorticosteroids with long-acting bronchodilators. Additional therapeutic options include phosphodiesterase-4 inhibitors, theophylline, and vaccination against influenza and pneumococcal infection [3]. Non-pharmacological interventions comprise smoking cessation, pulmonary rehabilitation, long-term oxygen therapy, respiratory support, and surgical procedures aimed at reducing lung hyperinflation or restoring lung function [13,14]. Alongside standard approaches, including antibacterial therapy for infectious exacerbations, treatment should target key pathogenic mechanisms of the disease, such as systemic inflammation, endothelial dysfunction, and oxidative stress [3,10].

Eliminating harmful exposures, such as smoking and long-term inhalation of polluted air, can significantly slow, and in some cases halt, COPD progression [14]. However, once the disease and associated pathologies develop, complete recovery is impossible, necessitating regular patient monitoring [2]. Systematic management of comorbid conditions in COPD can reduce exacerbation risk, slow the progression of concomitant diseases, and lower mortality [3,16]. Current research focuses on identifying effective strategies to improve survival in patients with COPD and chronic damage to other organs, including the kidneys [7,8]. Selecting the optimal management strategy for patients with coexisting COPD and chronic kidney disease remains a complex clinical challenge. A promising approach involves the use of drugs with anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, as well as agents capable of improving endothelial function [5,10].

Endothelial dysfunction (ED) is a pathological condition of the vascular inner lining, in which its key physiological functions are impaired. Under normal conditions, the endothelium maintains vascular homeostasis by regulating the balance between vasodilation and vasoconstriction, exerting antithrombotic and anti-inflammatory effects, and controlling the proliferation, migration, and apoptosis of vascular smooth muscle cells [5]. In ED, nitric oxide (NO) synthesis a potent vasodilator is reduced, while the production of endothelin-1 (ET-1) a strong vasoconstrictor increases, leading to impaired vessel relaxation [15]. Characteristic features of ED also include elevated expression of adhesion molecules such as ICAM-1 and VCAM-1, which promote leukocyte adherence to the vascular wall and infiltration, further enhancing inflammation and oxidative stress [11]. In addition, ED is associated with excessive generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reduced activity of antioxidant systems, resulting in cellular damage and sustaining chronic inflammation [9,10]. This combination of factors plays a critical role in the development of cardiovascular diseases, cardiorenal syndrome, chronic kidney disease, diabetes mellitus, and metabolic syndrome.

Systemic inflammation in COPD is accompanied by membrane-destructive processes in which lipid metabolism products prostaglandins and leukotrienes are released from damaged cell membranes. These substances are important mediators of inflammation and play a central role in endothelial injury [5]. A key pathogenic mechanism is the activation of inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-1 (IL-1), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α). These cytokines increase endothelial permeability, leading to impairment of the vascular barrier function and the development of endothelial dysfunction.

Endothelial dysfunction (ED) is considered an early marker of vascular disorders in COPD [15]. Its signs can be detected even in the initial stages of the disease and aggravate respiratory failure and systemic hypoxemia. This combination of inflammatory and vascular changes creates an unfavorable background for the progression not only of respiratory pathology but also of cardiovascular and renal diseases, highlighting the need for an integrated approach to COPD therapy.

Recent studies show that about one-third of the body's entire endothelial lining is located in the renal microcirculatory bed and large renal vessels. This makes the kidneys one of the primary targets for damaging factors, including in COPD [8]. Damage to the renal vascular endothelium is often accompanied by albuminuria a marker of diffuse endothelial injury, which is associated with increased cardiovascular and overall mortality [7]. Oxidative stress plays a significant role in the progression of ED and its related vascular complications. Its activation accelerates nitric oxide (NO) degradation, suppresses endothelial NO synthase expression, and promotes

hypercoagulation and endothelial cell apoptosis. Clinical and experimental data indicate a direct correlation between oxidative stress markers and the severity of ED [10,11].

In COPD, it is characteristic that even in the early stages, reduced bronchial patency leads to hypoxia, which impairs cellular energy metabolism due to mitochondrial respiratory chain dysfunction [5]. This is accompanied by tissue damage in various organs, including the kidneys, and activation of free radical processes. These processes are controlled by the body's antioxidant systems, which include enzymatic mechanisms (superoxide dismutase, catalase, glutathione peroxidase) and non-enzymatic mechanisms (ascorbic acid, α -tocopherol) [9]. Assessment of endotoxemia and oxidative stress levels in the blood of COPD patients is used to monitor disease severity and prognosis, underscoring the importance of their control in comprehensive therapy (GOLD, 2023). Free radical processes play a key role in the pathogenesis of many diseases, including ED, which justifies the need for their prevention and correction. Pathogenetically sound therapy includes the use of drugs that reduce excessive reactive oxygen species (ROS) synthesis, inhibit excessive lipid peroxidation, increase endogenous antioxidant system activity, restore cellular energy potential, and normalize metabolism [9,10]. Of particular interest are antihypoxants correctors of energy metabolism capable of preventing or partially reversing energy synthesis disorders and reducing the severity of functional cell impairments [11].

In COPD, where hypoxia is combined with activation of free radical oxidation, optimal therapeutic effect can be achieved using agents that have both antihypoxic and antioxidant properties [5].

Conclusion

Thus, the systemic manifestations of COPD may contribute to the development and mutual progression of renal dysfunction, necessitating a comprehensive treatment approach. At the same time, many aspects of the relationship between COPD and kidney pathology, as well as optimal methods for preventing and managing complications, remain insufficiently studied and require further research.

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